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Biofertilizer Its Effect on Degraded Ultisol, Soybean Nodulation and Yield

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Abstract

Soil fertility maintenance is a pre-condition for sustainable crop production especially in southeastern soils of Nigeria. Fertility restoration and reclamation efficiency of three treatments were evaluated on degraded ultisol using soybean as test crop in a greenhouse study conducted in completely randomized design experiment with four replications. The bio-fertilizer evaluated in this present study was; *Bracharia* grass + animal manure (BA), *Bracharia* grass + *Eupatorium odorata* + animal manure (BUA) and control soil (CO). The result findings indicated that fertility restoration and reclamation efficiency of the bio-fertilizer evaluated on the degraded ultisol was very highly positive that resulted in significant ($P < 0.05$) difference in soil parameters tested and increased growth and yield parameters of soybean. The degraded soil was enriched with high content of OC, CEC, available P, Ca, Mg and favorable pH level of which varied with the treatments. The structural stability of aggregates was greatly improved in amended soils relative to the degraded soil. The bio-fertilizer BA recorded; 162.68%, 150.80% and 152.22% of mean weight diameter, aggregate stability and moisture content respectively over the control soil. The yield parameters of soybean were highly influenced, dry matter yield showed 144.72% increase in the amended soils relative to the control soil. The results of this study is of evidence that bio-fertilizer, BA and BUA can efficiently reclaim and restore fertility of a degraded soil, encourage sustainable crop production and promote soil and water conservation

Keywords: Bio-fertilizer, compost, conservation, organic waste, soybean

Introduction

Soil fertility for crop production was successful managed in Nigeria and southeast in particular by shifting cultivation, whereby the soil fertility was naturally regenerated by bush fallow system. However, due to increased population and urbanization, as well as erosive conditions arising from heavy down pour, the arable agricultural land became limited thereby reducing the fallow period. In view of this therefore, low soil fertility, impoverishment, erosion and in extreme cases land degradation result. In trying to find solution to this problem of soil fertility, some cultural practices were applied. For instance, crop rotation and green manuring with various legumes, such as *calapagonium spp*, *crotalaria spp* etc. were set up using maize, rice, yam, cassava and groundnut as test crops. Nevertheless, the problem persisted since it was established that crop rotation and green manuring alone could not sustain continuous crop yield and soil fertility adequately. Subsequently the use of

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fossil fuel, and Nigeria as an exporting country led to the introduction of chemical fertilizer (inorganic) as a means of solving the fertility problem of the soils. Some of these soils are known to be infertile, low in OC, cations, CEC, P and N, since the colloidal minerals are mostly of low quality sesquioxides. But the application of the chemical fertilizer to the soil escalated the soil problems leading to structural degradation, nutrient imbalance, soil acidification etc. Lime was introduced as a remedial measure in combination with inorganic fertilizers. Though some measurable decrease in acidity were reported by Nweke (2020). But even when optimization of P availability was obtained in some soils, Udo and Uzu (1977), reported that liming of soil to pH5 and 6 produced more detrimental effects. It induced Mn, Zn and Mg deficiency in crops such as maize. Field studies using cassava peels mixed with animal droppings plus leaves based vermicompost, Mba (1996) and Nweke (2017) highlighted the beneficial effect of bio-fertilizer on cowpea and maize growth respectively, CEC and available P in southeast of Nigeria high rainfall acid soil. Furthermore, research by some workers has also shown that the application of bio-fertilizer not only increase crop production but helps to reduce the population of crop pest like nematode. For instance, it was noted that certain species of nematodes like *helicotylenchus* and *meloidogyne incognita* were considerable reduced following OM application (Patrick et al., 1965; Hunt et al., 1973; Tarjan, 1977; Chime et al., 2019). Addition of organic residues made of *Arachis hypogea*, peanut or *Azadirachta indica* in an amount of roughly 100kg/ha greatly reduced *meloidogyne* population, thereby increasing the yield of subsequently grown crops (Weischer, 1978). Thus, biofertilizers in form of OM is that alternative source of fertilizer due to its importance in soil and crop production as well as soil conservation. Unlike the inorganic fertilizer which supply only the nutrient elements. Bio-fertilizers not only supply the needed nutrient elements through microbial assistance but they in addition enhance crop production by ameliorating soil physical conditions by way of better aeration and better nutrient and water retention capacity.

Therefore, from the explanation given biological fertilizer is more effective and more dependable soil amendment which can enhance and sustain soil fertility for optimum crop yield and environmental health. It is also none toxic and serves as food for soil organisms. Since it is plant origin the natural nutrient balance ratio for most plant is adequate in it. Thus, the objective of this work is to evaluate the bio-fertilizer from two contrasting organic residues (*Bracharia spp* and *Chromolaena odorata*) plus two different animal manure, its effect on degraded ultisol, soybean nodulation and yield.

Materials and Methods

In this study *Bracharia spp* and *Chromolaena odorata* formerly *Eupatorium odoratum* were composted with animal manure in order to produce organic soil amendments. *Chromolaena odorata* serve as a source of organic materials in soils where it is growing, especially in forest soils. The weed grows rapidly, branches or tiller profusely and cover extensive areas. In this form it smothers or kills young weeds growing under it and concentrates moisture in the soil. The plant has characteristic pungent smell and as such unpalatable to sheep, goat and cattle. Therefore, these livestock try to avoid it. In rice production, it is often regarded as soil fertility indicator especially after the rain and the water have established. Among the local people and rural dwellers, the weed plant can be used in treating scratch and small wound.

Bracharia spp grass in its own case is a perennial grass, its creeping ability help in the smothering of young weeds growing underneath and concentrates moisture in the soil. The grass is of good quality pasture to the livestock as it can be prepared into silage or hay. Unlike the *chromolaena odorata*, the goat, sheep cattle and even rabbit eat the grass. The grass has highly competitive vigor. It enriches the soil whereby the decomposition of leaves and other organic residues release substantial number of nutrient elements.

Animal materials and mixtures

The organic wastes, pig and poultry were collected from piggery and poultry section of the animal science department of university of Nigeria Nsukka farm. Pig droppings were mixed with poultry droppings on fresh dry basis to form animal manure designated as A. The animal mixture is in the proportion of;

1kg pig:2kgpoultry = Animal manure (A).

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Compost mixture and quantity

Compost BA: Bracharia + Animal manure

10kg animal manure (A):10kg Bracharia grass (B). Total or quantity BA = 20kg

Compost BUA: Bracharia grass + Eupatorium residues + animal manure

Where; B = Bracharia grass,

U = Eupatorium residues

A = Animal manure

Quantity: 10kg animal manure:8kg Bracharia grass:2kg Eupatorium residues = 20kg BUA.

These were mixed thoroughly respectively and composted following the procedure already described in an earlier study Nweke (2013)

Potted soil sample

Soil samples (0-25cm) were collected from University of Nigeria Nsukka farm land and potted into 45 pots, the soil belong to Nkpologu series and classified as typic kandipaleustalt. While high yielding soybean was used as test crop.

The major component of the study is;

- a. Greenhouse study
- b. Laboratory study

Greenhouse study

Two hundred and fifty gram (250g) of BA and BUA respectively were weighed out and mixed thoroughly with 10kg soil and laid out in a completely randomized design (CRD). The experiment was replicated five (5) times. Five soybean seeds dressed with distilled water were planted per pot. After germination the stands were thinned down to three (3) stands/pot. At end of the seven (7) weeks study, the growth parameters, nodulation and dry matter yield were determined by counting, oven drying and weighing were applicable.

Laboratory study

Routine laboratory analysis was used to determine the properties of soil and amendments before mixing and planting and after harvest of the soybean.

The pH 1:2.5 solid to liquid ratio was determined in water. Available P determined by Bray and Kurtz (1945). Total N was done by the method of Bremner and Malvance (1982), while Jackson's method was used to determine the CEC. Organic carbon was determined by the method of Walkley and Black (1934). Ca and Mg was determined by the ammonium acetate saturation method using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Zang et al., 2012). Aggregate structural stability indices and water retention capacity as described by Obi (1990)

Data analysis

Data generated from the study were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were separated using least significant difference at 5% alpha level.

Results and Discussion

The results presented in Table 1, showed the physical and chemical properties of the soil, animal wastes, and biofertilizers before the initiation of the experiment. The result showed the soil class to be loamy sand, strongly acidic and very low in nutrient content, moisture retention was merely 5.403 and bulk density 1.316gcm^{-3} . The initial properties of BA and BUA biofertilizers and animal wastes used in the composition showed increase in nutrient content, water retention and aggregate stability (Table 1). Therefore, it is expected that the studied soil and soybean plant will benefit from the application of the biofertilizers.

Table 1. Nutrient content of soil, animal wastes and biofertilizer (BA and BUA).

Property	Soil	poultry	pig	Bracharia grass	Eupatorium residue	Compost BA	Compost BUA
Sand gkg ⁻¹	850						
Silt gkg ⁻¹	50						
Clay gkg ⁻¹	140						
TC	LS						
Dry matter		34.5	49.54	52.93	25.91		
pH H ₂ O	4.70					6.49	6.59
OC %	0.57	13.93	7.84			21.96	25.80
TN %	0.073	2.97	2.10			0.56	0.75
Avail. P mgkg ⁻¹	0.85	22.68	10.99			16.09	18.52
CEC cmolkg ⁻¹	8.00					10.46	13.59
Ca cmolkg ⁻¹	0.81	7.85	2.91			5.91	6.41
Mg cmolkg ⁻¹	0.52	5.54	1.85			2.61	3.95
Kcmolkg ⁻¹	0.15	1.53	0.65			0.85	0.96
Na cmolkg ⁻¹	0.11	0.72	0.44			0.51	0.45
Water retention	5.403					17.89	16.35
Aggregate stability %	57.87					99.14	99.17
BD gcm ⁻³	1.316						

On Farm observation

Germination was noticed in all the treatment on the 5th day after planting and by the 7th day, germination has completed because almost all the five seeds planted per pot have germinated. The growth of the soybean plant in treated soils was rapid with broad leaves as compared to untreated soils where the leaves are small in size, stem tiny and growth retarded. The growth rate in the control soil was not rapid and the leaves were shriveled and looked like something hot water was poured upon. The nodules harvested from the untreated soils were found to be tiny and small in size compared to the treated soils that were big in size. Further the number harvested per pot is small in untreated soil. In soils treated with BA and BUA bio-fertilizer, the nodules harvested are large in size, and the number harvested per pot was relatively large compared to the untreated soils.

Effect of bio fertilizer BA and BUA on physicochemical properties of the degraded ultisol

The physicochemical properties of the studied soil presented in Table 2 indicated significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among the treatments evaluated except for Mg and DR results. The physical parameters result showed BA treatment to have enhanced the soil more than the other treatments. The result value of MWD, DR, aggregate stability and MC showed a variation of BA>BUA>CO. The percentage increase in BA of MWD, aggregate stability and MC over the control soil were; 162.68%, 150.80% and 151.22% respectively. The observed increased value in the amended soils could be associated to bio fertilizer application and the activities of the soil microbes in bio fertilizer decomposition leading to cementing effect on the soil particles or may be a reflection of its clay content or may be the presence of Al³⁺ ion that promote high structure and stability of soil aggregates especially in low activity clay soil like ultisol. The scenario in part or in all may have contributed to the recorded result of the soil physical parameters. Nweke (2016, 2019a) reported that organic waste incorporation significantly enhanced the structure and stability of soil aggregates. The moisture content capacity of the treated soils was by 151.22% greater than the control soil, meaning that soil solution and all that dissolved therein and water transmission in the studied soil is very much enhanced. Dissolved nutrient absorption is very much in partnership with water transmission in soil and can be used to predict crop responses

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to soil moisture conditions and help to understand the soil-root-leaf continuum (Pfister et al., 2014; Evaristo et al., 2015; Foster et al., 2016).

The acidity nature of the soil was reduced following the addition of bio-fertilizer of which increase in pH level on the amended soil varied from 1.10-1.12 over the control soil value. The recorded values of OC, pH, Ca and Mg showed that BUA recorded higher values relative to the other treatments. The percentage increase in OC, Ca and Mg over the recorded value in control soil were; 364.62%, 110.96% and 128.85% respectively. While the recorded value of TN, available P and CEC showed result variation of BA>BUA>CO. The difference in value recorded between the BA and BUA merely range between 0.07-1.27 when the three parameters are considered together, while the percentage increase in available P and CEC in BA relative to control soil was 362.83 and 113.20% respectively. The value recorded for the chemical parameters of the soil is of evident that the addition of bio-fertilizer enriched the studied soil with the chemical nutrients. This probably may be associated with higher content of nutrients in the bio-fertilizer applied of which might have energized the soil microbial activities leading to mineralization of plant nutrients into available forms following OM decomposition, reducing the available P fixation and increasing the OC content so that the soil can effectively hold cations in the exchangeable form. The findings corroborate the works of Nweke (2019b). The productivity effect of this result is observed in the yield parameters of soybean recorded in Table 3.

Table 2. Effect of bio-fertilizer BA and BUA on physicochemical properties of the studied soil

Treatment	MWD mm	DR	Agg. Stab. %	MC %	pH H ₂ O	OC %	TN	Av. P mgkg ⁻¹	CEC	Ca cmolkg ⁻¹	Mg
BA	5.49	0.89	21.97	50.27	6.75	2.95	0.53	12.45	10.47	4.01	1.68
BUA	4.96	0.84	18.79	34.74	6.84	3.02	0.46	11.84	9.20	4.81	2.45
CO (soil)	2.09	0.75	8.76	20.01	5.65	0.65	0.13	2.69	4.91	2.28	1.08
LSD 0.05	1.36	NS	2.67	3.37	0.45	0.35	0.05	1.59	1.35	0.75	NS

Effect of bio-fertilizer on the soybean growth and yield

The yield and yield component of soybean recorded in Table 3 showed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among the treatments an indication that the incorporation of the bio-fertilizer positively influenced the growth and yield parameters of soybean. Following organic wastes incorporation in soil, Nwaigwe et al. (2013) and Nweke (2019) reported increased yield of potato of different varieties and maize respectively. Apart from leaf area and dry matter that showed increased value in BUA, every other parameter such as plant height, number of nodule and weight of nodule showed increased value in BA treatment relative to other treatments. The percentage increase in number of nodules, weight of nodule in BA and dry matter yield in BUA relative to the control soil were; 1982.10%, 8751.85% and 144.72% respectively. The evidence of this result could be attributed to the capacity of the microbial activities in mineralization and mobilization in converting unavailable plant nutrients from organic form to available inorganic forms that the soybean required for adequate growth, development and yield recorded in this study.

Table 3. Effect of BA and BUA compost on soybean yield and yield components

Treatment	Plant height cm	Leaf area cm ²	Number of nodules	Weight of nodule g	Dry matter yield g
BA	56.45	28.70	238.48	4.78	35.50
BUA	54.11	29.98	191.24	3.48	43.78
CO (soil)	41.35	8.71	11.45	0.054	17.89
LSD 0.05	1.14	0.43	3.80	0.53	4.06

Conclusion

The ability of any bio-fertilizer made from organic residues to ameliorate nutrient deficient soil release plant nutrients in available form and improved crop yield is dependent on the nutrient content of the residues, rate of decomposition, type and nature of microbes present in the soil. Based on the findings of the study bio-fertilizer

from organic residues have shown promises as excellent soil amendment material for improving soil productivity and maintaining their biological activities. This account for the improved soil pH, OC, available P, CEC and other tested chemical parameters as well as aggregate stability, MC and MWD. These may have accounted for the improvement recorded in the yield and yield components of soybean. The fertilizing status of the soil was imparted due to enhancement level of soil pH and essential plant nutrients. Therefore, it is concluded that bio-fertilizer from organic residues are very useful as soil amendment, improved physicochemical properties of the degraded soil and essential plant nutrients contained in the bio-fertilizer is released to the extent that it supported soybean growth and yield. Field trials is however, suggested to confirm the results of this explanatory greenhouse study.

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